

Project number: 874662
Project Acronym: HEAP

Project Title: Human Exposome Assessment Platform

Project Website URL:

Project Coordinator: Joakim Dillner

Organisation: KI

E-mail: Joakim.Dillner@ki.se

Work Package 5
Sensor pilot documentation

Work package Leader: Ville Pimenoff

Organisation: UOULU

E-Mail: ville.pimenoff@oulu.fi

Project Deliverable

D5.4: Sensor pilot Documentation

Deliverable due date: 2023-12-31

Document history

Version	Date	Changes	By	Reviewed
0.1	2023-12-31	Finalized draft	Ville Pimenoff, Matti Lehtinen	Ville Pimenoff

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable contains information about the legal basis of the cohort entitled '*Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device*' and described in detail in WP5 D5.1. Enclosed is the final version of study protocol as submitted by UOULU (Pimenoff-Lehtinen) to the local institutional ethics committee in Finland, ethics approvals for the registration number of the clinical study in Finland (UOULU) and approved documentation for the invitation/enrolment of study participants and data management.

This deliverable describes the wearable UPAS v2.0 (Ultrasonic Personal Air Sampler, <https://www.accsensors.com/products>) exposometer cohort trial documentation. The wearable sensor cohort in HEAP consists of healthy pregnant and non-pregnant women (N=100) followed up for at least four months with systematic longitudinal sampling using wearables devices and urine sampling. Our careful recruitment and monitoring of the cohort's individuals provide the basis for the wearable sensors cohort, which enables the joint longitudinal assessment of the individual's abiotic and biotic exposome and their interaction with different exposome components at individual level.

Ethical review board approved informed documentation, due data protection/authority approvals WP5 makes the wearable sensor cohort available for a pilot proof-of-concept study in monitoring abiotic and biotic exposome during pregnancy with a wearable device. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic the wearable sensor cohort participants recruitment was delayed by one year and the cohort monitoring of 100 women is currently 92% completed and the remaining participants monitoring will be completed by the end of February 2024.

All procedures performed in the WP5 cohort involving data from human participants are in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional research committee in Finland, and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards.

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
2	Introduction	5
3	Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device... Error!	
	Bookmark not defined.	
3.1	Research Study protocol	6
3.2	Ethics approval for the cohort registration, enrollment and data	9
4	Summary.....	12
5	References	13
6	Appendix 1. Informed consent of the study.....	14

2 Introduction

Exposome refers to all the exposures through one's lifetime, which has a significant impact on personal health. Our and others' published work suggests that we are exposed to a dazzling array of abiotic and biotic environmental contaminants in our daily lives, far beyond what was previously quantified and understood (Jiang et al. 2018, Zhou et al. 2019).

Deliverable 5.4 comprises documentation demonstrating that the informed documentation, consenting procedures and recruitment of the cohort entitled 'Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device', is in accordance with the current EU-requirements so that the cohorts can contribute to the exposure assessment studies of the HEAP platform.

Enclosed is the final version of the study protocol as submitted by UOULU (Pimenoff/Lehtinen) to the regional medical research ethics committee of the Wellbeing services county of North Ostrobothnia in Finland, ethics approvals with registration number of the clinical study in Finland (UOULU) and approved documentation required for invitation/enrolment of study participants and data management.

This deliverable describes the wearable UPAS v2.0 (Ultrasonic Personal Air Sampler, <https://www.accsensors.com/products>) exposometer cohort trial documentation. The wearable sensor cohort in HEAP consists of healthy pregnant and non-pregnant women (N=100) followed up for at least four months with systematic longitudinal sampling using wearables devices and blood/urine sampling. Our careful recruitment and monitoring of the cohort's individuals provide the basis for the wearable cohort, which enables the joint longitudinal assessment of the individual's abiotic and biotic exposome and their interaction.

Ethical review board approved informed documentation, due data protection/authority approvals WP5 makes the wearable sensor cohort available for a pilot proof-of-concept study in monitoring abiotic and biotic exposome during pregnancy with a wearable device. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic the wearable sensor cohort participants recruitment could only be started in 2023 and the cohort monitoring of 100 women is currently 92% completed and the remaining participants monitoring will be completed by the end of February 2024.

All procedures performed in the WP5 cohort involving data from human participants are in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional research committee in Finland, following the Finnish Biobank Act §26 & §27 and National GDPR regulations.

3 Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device

3.1 Research study protocol

Preterm birth (PTB), occurring before the 37th week of pregnancy, is a widespread occurrence, affecting 5% to 18% of pregnancies worldwide (Romero et al., 2014). Notably, it stands as the leading cause of neonatal deaths (Liu et al., 2012). The Nordic countries, with Finland at the forefront, are recognized for their low rates of neonatal deaths, well-documented by population-based medical birth registers (Langhoff-Ross et al., 2014). The genetically unique Finnish population and the consistently stable incidence of PTB at 5% per pregnancy over the last decades (Jakobsson et al., 2008, www.thl.fi) provide a conducive setting for etiological studies on PTB.

While vascular disorders and uterine overdistension are recognized causes of preterm birth, recent research has highlighted additional factors (Figure 1). These range from alterations in the lower genital tract microbiome during pregnancy, pathogenic infections, and associated cervical diseases in pregnant women to disruptions in immunological tolerance between the fetus and the mother, as well as decidual senescence, often associated with environmental stress or genetic factors (Kyrgiou et al., 2016; Habbema et al., 2017; Fettweis et al., 2019; Romero et al., 2014; Tiensuu et al., 2020). While the role of human papillomavirus (HPV) infection in PTB is diminishing, the remaining causes' population attributable proportions, potential future targets for intervention, are yet to be determined (Heinonen et al., 2014; Kalliala et al., 2020).

Wearable sensors, such as those for skin and air, offer the possibility of health monitoring outside hospitals. Frequent sampling of sweat and saliva allows for exposure determination through molecular composition, facilitating multi-omics profiling. These methodologies may eventually enable accurate and non-invasive prediction of changes in an individual's health using frequently sampled sensor data.

A multi-omics approach, encompassing immunome, transcriptome, microbiome, proteome, and metabolome adaptations during pregnancy, has identified immune clockworks that define the transition from the tolerogenic immunophenotype of the fetoplacental unit to a pro-inflammatory phenotype, contributing to PTB (Ghaeni et al., 2019; Peterson et al., 2020; Thaxton et al., 2009; Marcellin et al., 2017; Frascoli et al., 2018).

This pilot study aims to assess the feasibility of wearable sensors and multi-omics profiling in pregnant Finnish women for sensor-based health and pregnancy monitoring (Dunn et al., 2018). Leveraging the country-wide Finnish Vaccine Cohort (F-VAC) and Finnish Maternity Cohort (FMC) study infrastructures, as well as the Finnish Medical Birth Registry at the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), we will enroll participants for the use of multi-omics devices, blood, saliva, and skin sweat patch sampling, followed by comprehensive follow-up (Langhoff-Ross et al., 2014; Lehtinen et al., 2015; Lehtinen et al., 2017).

Figure 1. Causes of preterm birth (amended from Romero et al. 2014).

Enrollment:

From 2022 to 2023, we will extend invitations to consecutive pregnant women attending municipal maternity health care at the 12th week of gestation. Participants will provide informed consent (see Appendix 1) to wear two wearable devices: 1) the environmental Ultrasonic Personal Aerosol Sampler (UPAS) v.2.0 (Access Sensor Technologies)[1], 2) a smart device for health data (Firstbeat), and 3) a skin sweat absorbent patch technique for collecting skin sweat for exposure estimation. Participants will attend four visits to F-VAC study sites in various locations. In addition non-pregnant controls will be enrolled from the same study sites, with 100 consented pregnant and nonpregnant participants in total.

Wearable Sensors and Exposure Devices:

Study participants will carry the Ultrasonic Personal Aerosol Sampler (UPAS) v.2.0 and a smart device (Sensomics/Firstbeat) health data logger for 4 to 6 months during gestational weeks 12 to 36. These wearable sensors are safe, non-hazardous devices worn as a shoulder band (UPAS exposometer) or a smartphone-connected wristwatch/skin patch (health data logger). Participants will also be instructed to change the particle collecting filter in the UPAS device every two weeks and wear Firstbeat health data /skin patches for at least one week at the beginning and end of both two-month monitoring periods. The skin sweat absorbent patch will be worn on the side/back skin for 24-48 hours at the start and end of both two-month monitoring periods. All digital data from the wearable sensors will be collected following European GDPR legislation and Finnish ethics committee approval for the cohort PI Dr. Ville Pimenoff for secure digital storage and analyses of the wearables data accessible only to the researchers involved in the study.

Sampling:

Two blood samples will be collected at Finnish healthcare study sites during the 2nd and 3rd trimester of pregnancy (approximately between gestational weeks 12 and 36). Additionally, two urine samples will be collected at the same study sites during the 2nd and 3rd trimester of

pregnancy. The filters, collecting biotic and abiotic particles from the air, will be sent by participants to the health clinic for chemical and biological data storage and later timepoint analysis.

UPAS filters will be divided into two parts for abiotic (ie. chemical) and biotic (ie. biological) analyses. For microbial analysis, at least 5ng of total DNA/RNA will be extracted, followed by HiSeq metagenomic or RNA sequencing. Species and strain-level microbial composition will be determined using *de novo* assembly tools such as MEGAHIT (Mas-Lloret et al. 2020) and detection algorithms, such as MetaPhlan2 (Truong et al. 2015) and Kraken2 (Woods 2019). Strain-specific microbial classification and phylogenomics will be deployed using in-house mapping and RAXML scripts in CSC sensitive data secure computing environment (Truong et al. 2017).

Cytokine Analyses:

Serum samples will be applied on a Luminex platform for cytokine analysis.

Registry Linkage:

Permission for consent-based linkage between the study register and the Finnish Medical Birth Registry using participants' personal identifiers will be sought from THL's Finn-Data.

Statistical Analyses and Modeling:

Various statistical analyses will be performed based on specific objectives and corresponding statistical analysis plans. R and python will be used for all statistical analyses. For predictive modelling, we will employ eg. the Elastic Net (EN) and XGBoost algorithms (described in D6.3 and D6.4), validated to measure the ability of separate datasets to predict abiotic and biotic exposome components using wearables data.

Time-table:

Enrollment will occur from 2022 to 2023, study visits will conclude by the end of February 2024, and analysis, modeling, and report writing will be completed by the end of 2024.

3.2 Ethics approval for the cohort registration, enrollment and data

Clinical study registration

This study is registered by the regional medical research ethics committee of the Wellbeing services county of North Ostrobothnia in Finland with a code 'HEAP_exposures', entitled as 'Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device- a HEAP pilot study' with an ethical review board registration number 120/2020. The PI with the ethical approval and responsibility of the cohort and related study is Dr. Ville Pimenoff from UOULU, Finland.

Approved research documentation available for invited participants

We invite you to participate in this research, which examines the possibility of measuring pregnancy-related exposures in women aged 25-35 in Finland during the years 2022-2023.

The study is conducted at the research stations of Tampere University (TAU) in Helsinki, Jyväskylä, Kotka, Kuopio, Lahti, Oulu, Pori, Rauma, Tampere, and Turku. You are invited to participate in this study because you are a woman aged 25-35. A total of 100 pregnant and non-pregnant women are invited to participate in this study. This notice describes the research and your potential role in it. After taking the time to review this notice, you will have the opportunity to ask questions about the study. If you decide to participate in the study, your consent to participate will be requested.

Purpose

The purpose of this study is to investigate whether it is possible to examine environmental abiotic and biotic exposures during pregnancy (weeks 12-36) using the UPAS device (Ultrasonic Personal Aerosol Sampler). The information provided by the device will be compared to functions measured by a smart device (e.g., heart rate), the cytokine profile indicating resistance measured from blood samples, and abiotic exposures from urine. With the information obtained, the aim is to assess whether portable devices can be used to identify exposures that may increase the risk of preterm birth, for example. In addition to pregnant individuals, non-pregnant controls are needed for the study.

The Regional Ethics Committee of Oulu University Hospital's has reviewed the research plan and provided a favorable opinion on it.

Principle investigator of the study

The person responsible for this cohort and related investigation is Dr. Ville Pimenoff, docent at the University of Oulu. The registry holder for the study is University of Oulu, which is responsible for the legality of the processing of personal data in connection with the study.

Course of the enrollement and study

If you participate in this study, you will have six visits to our research station (two two-month study periods) at the age of 25–35.

During the visits:

1. On the first visit, you will be asked to sign this consent document, and your suitability for the study will be checked.
2. You will be asked to take possession of and carry with you at all times a device called UPAS, which is the size of a mobile phone, during two two-month periods. The device collects airborne particles on a filter, from which biological and chemical environmental exposures can be determined. The filter needs to be changed every two weeks, and the used filters will be sent to the research station.
3. You will be asked to take possession of and carry with you daily a firstbeat smart device for four weeks. These devices record heart rate.

4. You will be asked to wear a patch-like sticker on your skin for two days during both study periods. The sticker collects a sample for the examination of microbial profiles and particles. The sticker is stored in the freezer.
5. You will provide a urine sample at all study visits (6 visits) to determine the microbial profile of the mucous membranes.
6. At four study visits, a nurse will take one tube (9ml) of blood from your elbow for the determination of your body's resistance profile based on cytokines.
7. For pregnant participants, the research nurse will contact you later to request information about the duration of your pregnancy.

Benefits and Potential Risks and Harms Related to the Study

The study aims to explore the possibility of measuring prenatal abiotic and biotic exposures using a portable device. The measurements collected during pregnancy will be compared with the resistance profile of the body, as indicated by the cytokine profile in blood samples, and the abiotic profiles of the urine. Participants in this study will receive a personal report on their participation and the study results. Real-time measurements from the smart device will be available on your smartphone. While the results are not likely to provide direct individual benefits, this study may, in the long term, help determine whether a portable device measuring exposure can monitor pregnant individuals for factors that may increase the risk of preterm birth. Blood sampling may cause bruising at the puncture site. Blood sampling and the collection of mucous membrane samples may also cause discomfort. The Firstbeat sensor and the adhesive patch may irritate the skin.

Processing of Personal Data and Confidentiality of Information

Your personal data will be processed for the purpose of the scientific research described above. The legal basis for the processing of personal data is the public interest, and for special categories of personal data, such as health-related data, the legal basis is the public interest in scientific research and public health, including ensuring high-quality and safety standards for healthcare, pharmaceuticals, and medical devices (General Data Protection Regulation, Article 6(1)(e), 9(2)(j), and 9(2)(i)).

Only the necessary personal data for the purpose of the study will be recorded in the secure registry in Finland. The information collected about you and the study results will be handled confidentially in accordance with the legislation governing the processing of personal data. The participant's name, personal identification number, and contact information will be replaced with an individual identification code. Your information and the samples collected from you will be stored in the research material in a coded form, and reference to you will only be made with the identification code.

The research material and your information, as part of it, will also be analyzed in a coded form, ensuring that an individual person cannot be directly identified without a separate code key.

This code key, which allows the identity of an individual participant and their research data to be linked, will be kept by designated PI and local research nurse coordinator in Oulu University (UOULU).

Final research results will be reported at the group level. Identification of individual participants is not possible from publications or reports on the research results.

In the study, the following information from you will be collected from the following sources: Information provided during the study visit and laboratory results related to the samples provided.

Coded information and samples related to you in the study will be handled by the research personnel conducting this study and the staff of the collaborating research laboratories. Pseudonymized Anonymous (direct personal identifiers removed, and identification of the participant is not otherwise possible) research data will be stored on the computer of the Center for Scientific Computing (CSC) in Finland.

Information obtained from this study regarding the measurement possibilities of prenatal exposures will be published in scientific journals after the completion of the study.

All parties and individuals handling your information are bound by confidentiality.

Storage of Your Personal Data: The research nurses at each research station will keep the research material of their research station in locked rooms and cabinets. Computers are protected with a username and password. Non-electronic and electronic materials containing personal information are kept in locked rooms accessible only to designated individuals authorized for their tasks.

The storage of information related to you is managed by the research nurse and PI of the cohort. Pseudonymized Anonymous data is stored on the computer of the Center for Scientific Computing (CSC), the State Data Center. The storage period of your information is governed by legislation and good clinical research practice. Samples collected during the study and related information will be kept in UOULU by Pimenoff.

Participation of the study

Participation in this study is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or discontinue your participation at any time during the study without providing a reason, and it will not result in any harm to you. Refusing or discontinuing the study will not affect your right to receive the necessary care for your condition.

You may also withdraw your consent at any time during the study without providing reasons by notifying the research staff. Withdrawing your consent will not cause any harm to you. If you decide to withdraw your consent, or if your participation in the study is discontinued for any

other reason, the information collected up to that point may still be used in this study if it is required for the study's completion, and if the law permits or requires it.

4 Summary

This deliverable contains the legal documentation of the cohort entitled '*Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device*' and described in detail in WP5 D5.1.

Increased opportunities to monitor the physiology of the body, environmental exposures, and their interaction have rapidly emerged through the use of wearable monitoring devices. The purpose of the wearable sensors study is to assess the possibilities of measuring environmental exposures during pregnancy and compare them with data collected from participants on the body's immunity, mucosal microbes, and general physiological functions. Our study pilots the potential to investigate comprehensively the causes of preterm birth (5% of births) in a broader sample. This pilot study is conducted at the University of Tampere's HPV Vaccine Study research stations in Oulu and Tampere, by the research nurses at these stations and led by PI Ville Pimenoff.

Enclosed is the final version of study protocol as submitted by UOULU (Pimenoff-Lehtinen) to the local institutional ethics committee in Finland, ethics approvals with registration number of the clinical study in Finland (UOULU) and approved documentation for the invitation/enrolment of study participants and data management.

Requested documentation and information for this deliverable are the following:

1. Final version of the study protocol for Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device- a HEAP pilot study is described in 3.1. of this document.
2. Registration of the study with number 120/2020 by the regional medical research ethics committee of the Wellbeing services county of North Ostrobothnia in Finland with a code 'HEAP_exposures', entitled as 'Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device- a HEAP pilot study'.
3. The ethical approvals and responsibility of the cohort data management for the 'Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device' study is approved for Ville Pimenoff from UOULU, Finland. The enrolment of the study is ethically justified and through the EU's Horizon 2020 HEAP network, the necessary resources are available for its implementation.

5 References

- Dunn J, et al. Wearables and the medical revolution. *Per Medicine* 2018;15:429-48.
- Fettweis JM, et al. The vaginal microbiome and preterm birth. *Nature Med* 2019; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-019-0450-2>.
- Frascoli M, et al. Alloreactive fetal T cells promote uterine contractility in preterm labor via IFN-gamma and TNF-alpha. *Sci Trans Med* 2018;10:eaan2263.
- Ghaemi MS, et al. Multi-omics modeling of the immunome, transcriptome, microbiome, proteome and metabolome adaptations during human pregnancy. *Bioinformatics* 2019;35:95-103.
- Habbema D, et al. Harms of cervical cancer screening in the United States and the Netherlands. *Int J Cancer*. 2017;140:1215-22.
- Heinonen A, et al. Risk of preterm birth in women with cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade one: a population-based cohort study *Acta Obst Gyn Scand* 2014;97:135-41.
- Jakobsson M, et al. The incidence of preterm birth deliveries decreases in Finland. *Br J Obstetrics Gynecol* 2008;115:38-43.
- Jiang, C. et al. Dynamic Human Environmental Exposome Revealed by Longitudinal Personal Monitoring. *Cell* **175**, 277–291.e31, 2018.
- Kalliala I, et al. Reduced preterm birth rate after bivalent HPV vaccination: registry-based follow-up of a randomized clinical trial. *Prev Med* 2020.
- Klous L, et al. The effect of sweat sample storage condition on sweat content. *Temperature* 2021 15;8(3):254-61.
- Kyrgiou M, et al. Adverse obstetric outcomes after local treatment for cervical preinvasive and early invasive disease according to cone depth: systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ*. 2016;354:i3633.
- Langhoff-Ross J, et al. The Nordic medical birth registers – a potential goldmine for clinical research. *Acta Obst Gyn Scand* 2014;93:132-7.
- Lehtinen M, et al. Characteristics of a cluster-randomized, phase IV human papillomavirus vaccination effectiveness trial. *Vaccine* 2015;33:1284-90.
- Lehtinen M, et al. Cancer registry follow-up for 17M person-yrs of a nationwide maternity cohort. *Cancer Med* 2017;6:3060-4.
- Lehtinen M, et al. Impact of gender-neutral or girls-only vaccination against HPV. Results of a community randomized trial (I). *Int J Cancer* 2018;142:949-58.
- Lehtinen M, et al. Effectiveness of AS04-adjuvanted human papillomavirus (HPV) type 16/18 vaccine in reducing oropharyngeal HPV infections in young females – results from a community-randomized trial. *Int J Cancer* 2020;147:170-4.
- Marcellin L, et al. Immune modifications in fetal membranes overlying the cervix precede parturition in humans. *J Immunol* 2017;198:1345-56.
- Mas-Lloret J, et al. Gut microbiome diversity detected by high-coverage 16S and shotgun sequencing of paired stool and colon sample. *Sci Data* 2020;7:92.
- Nurk S, Meleshko D, Korobeynikov A, Pevzner PA. metaSPAdes: a new versatile metagenomic assembler. *Genome Res*. 2017 May;27(5):824-834.
- Romero R, et al. Preterm labor: One syndrome, many causes. *Science* 2014;345:760-5.
- Sailani MR, et al. Deep longitudinal multiomics profiling reveals two biological seasonal patterns in California. *Nature Commun* 2020; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18758-1>.
- Thaxton JE, et al. TLR9 activation coupled to IL-10 deficiency induces adverse pregnancy outcomes. *J Immunol* 2009;183:1144-54.
- Tiensuu H, et al. Risk of spontaneous preterm birth and fetal growth associates with fetal SLIT2. *PLoS Genet* (6): e1008107, 2019.

- Truong DT, et al. MetaPhlan2 for enhanced metagenomic taxonomic profiling. *Nat Methods*. 2015 Oct;12(10):902-3. doi: 10.1038/nmeth.3589.
- Truong DT, et al. Microbial strain-level population structure and genetic diversity from metagenomes. *Genome Res* 2017;27:626-38.
- Volckens J, et al.. Development and evaluation of an ultrasonic personal aerosol sampler. *Indoor Air* 2017; 27:409–16.
- Wild, C. P. Complementing the genome with an 'exposome': the outstanding challenge of environmental exposure measurement in molecular epidemiology. *Cancer Epidemiol. Biomarkers Prev.* **14**, 1847–1850 (2005).
- Wood DE, Lu J, Langmead B. Improved metagenomic analysis with Kraken 2. *Genome Biol.* 2019 Nov 28;20(1):257.
- Zhou, W. et al. Longitudinal multi-omics of host–microbe dynamics in prediabetes. *Nature* 569(7758):663-671, 2019.

6 Appendix 1. Informed consent of the study

Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device

I have been invited to participate in the above-mentioned scientific study. I have read and understood the information provided to me about the study. I have received sufficient clarification about the study and the collection, processing, and disclosure of my personal information associated with it. The content of the study has also been explained to me verbally, and I have received satisfactory answers to all my questions about the study. The information was provided to me by (_____ University of Tampere/University of Oulu).

I have received sufficient information about my rights as a participant, the purpose and implementation of the study, as well as the benefits and risks of the study. I have had enough time to consider my participation in the study.

I understand that participation in this study is voluntary. I have the right to refuse to participate and withdraw my consent to the study at any time during the research without providing reasons by notifying the research staff.

I understand that my information will be treated confidentially. In connection with the study, my personal data may be transferred or disclosed in coded form, securely, to parties outside the research group (not outside Finland) or used in scientific publications as described in the research information.

Refusing to participate in the study or withdrawing consent will not have negative consequences for me and will not affect my treatment or care in any way. I am aware that if I withdraw my consent or if my participation in the study is discontinued for any other reason, the information collected up to that point may still be processed in this study, if necessary for the conduct of the study, and if legislation allows or requires it.

With my signature, I confirm my participation in this study and voluntarily consent to being a participant. I understand that my health-related and other personal information will be processed as part of this study.